

Steering microbial communities via the lactate route to selectively produce high concentrations of propionate from food waste

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Two-stage fermentation
Mixed cultures
Eco-engineering
Short chain fatty acids
Waste valorisation
Bioconversion

ABSTRACT

Propionate is a valuable platform chemical, in particular as a precursor for the production of sustainable jet fuel. However, its biological production remains a challenge, particularly in mixed-culture waste fermentation, where a mixture of volatile fatty acids is typically generated with a low propionate selectivity. This study investigates a two-stage fermentation process to convert food waste into propionate using two different inocula. The strategy relies on driving microbial metabolism toward lactate production in the first-stage fermentation, which will serve as the intermediate for propionate production during the second step of the fermentation. With both inocula, lactate was effectively consumed and preferentially converted into propionate and acetate, with propionate concentrations reaching up to $17.90 \pm 0.35 \text{ g L}^{-1}$, representing $45.51 \pm 1.81\%$ of total COD metabolites. This production was associated with the growth of *Anaerosporebacter*, *Tyzzarella* and some *Clostridium* genera, in both inocula, suggesting their pivotal role in the lactate-propionate pathway. Overall, these results demonstrate that a two-stage fermentation strategy can efficiently target high propionate concentrations and reasonable selectivity using mixed cultures, by specifically targeting the lactate-propionate pathway, regardless of the initial inoculum.

1. Introduction

The transition toward a circular, bio-based economy has heightened interest in the microbial production of volatile fatty acids (VFAs) as renewable platform chemicals. VFAs such as acetate, butyrate, and propionate serve as valuable intermediates for the production of bio-fuels, bioplastics, solvents, and food preservation agents, offering sustainable alternatives to fossil-derived chemicals [1,2]. Propionate is especially promising due to its versatility as a precursor for poly-hydroxyalkanoates (PHA), biological nutrient removal, or acetoin production from renewable resources, thereby supporting the cascade conversion of organic wastes into valuable products up to sustainable jet fuels [3–5].

Fermentation of organic waste streams is one of the most promising processes for VFA production, as it combines waste valorisation with biochemical synthesis of valuable chemicals. More particularly, food waste (FW) stands out as an abundant and energy-rich resource. Its high carbohydrate (from 5 to 70% Total Solids - TS), protein (from 9.8 to 29.6% TS), and lipid content (from 0 to 26.7% TS) [6], combined with its low lignin content, make it relevant for anaerobic fermentation [7,8].

However, FW fermentation with mixed microbial cultures typically yields a broad mixture of VFAs with low selectivity, as multiple metabolic pathways coexist and compete for organic substrates. This lack of control limits the accumulation of specific products such as propionate and makes the downstream recovery more complicated [9–11].

To overcome these limitations, several strategies have been explored to drive and control fermentation pathways. Specifically, the use of suitable substrates, such as crude glycerol and cheese whey, has been shown to promote propionate production [9,12]. Pre-treatments and additives that favour targeted microbial metabolisms have also shown potential, although these approaches often require higher operational costs and may not be broadly applicable to the diversity of waste types [13–17].

Propionate can be produced through various fermentation routes, including the Wood-Werkman cycle, the succinate pathway, the acrylate pathway, and the propanediol pathway [18–21]. These pathways involve lactate as a key intermediate, supporting the use of a two-stage fermentation strategy, where lactate is first produced and subsequently converted into propionate. Such two-stage fermentation systems are particularly attractive for complex wastes, as each step can be optimised

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independently to favour specific microbial activities, and this allows targeting propionate and acetate as main products, increasing propionate selectivity. Most studies investigating the FW - lactate – propionate route relied on the bioaugmentation with *Propionibacterium* sp. or *Acidipropionibacterium* sp. in the second stage [22–25]. These approaches, while effective for achieving high and selective propionate production, relied on the pre-cultivation of pure cultures and may be challenging to scale up. In contrast, Wu et al. [26] applied a two-stage fermentation process with mixed cultures without bioaugmentation, achieving a propionate concentration of 3 g L^{-1} , being the main product, but with remaining butyrate production of up to 1.5 g L^{-1} . These findings suggest that the FW–lactate–propionate route using mixed cultures can be a promising strategy for propionate production from biowaste, but they also reveal important limitation, notably the persistence of metabolic competition leading to the formation of undesirable by-products such as butyrate, and the difficulty in achieving sufficient propionate concentrations for further use.

The present study aims to address these limitations by investigating a two-stage fermentation strategy to improve both the selectivity and the concentration of propionate production from FW. This sequential conversion approach allows each fermentation stage to be optimised individually toward a specific product through adjustments of the operating parameters. In the first stage, a lactate-enriched effluent is generated using different mixed cultures, which is subsequently converted to propionate in a second fermentation stage. Unlike previous studies relying on pure cultures or simple substrates, this work exploits microbial diversity and evaluates steering mixed microbial communities toward the selective production of propionate from food waste. The innovation of this work lies in controlling mixed microbial communities using lactate as the unique driver, thereby targeting propionate production while limiting the production of competing metabolites. Different inocula were evaluated to investigate the role of microbial community composition in propionate production and to identify their contribution to the different conversion stages.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Inoculum and substrate

The substrate consisted of a model FW reconstituted from frozen products. The mixture was composed, on a fresh mass basis, of 15% meat, 10% yogurt, 15% red fruits, 10% breaded fish, 20% French fries, 15% vegetables (including carrots, broccoli, mushrooms, green beans, and potatoes), and 15% bread. It contained 59% carbohydrates, 13% lipids, and 21% proteins according to the packaging information. The total solids (TS) content was 33.47%, while the volatile solids (VS) content was 32.51%, resulting in a VS/TS ratio of 0.971 g VS/g TS. The initial pH was 5.32 ± 0.03 . The Flash BMP® (Flash Biochemical Methane Potential) [27], which relies on near-infrared spectroscopy measurements to estimate the BMP of a substrate, indicates a methane potential of $421.7 \text{ mL CH}_4 \text{ g VS}^{-1}$. Based on this value, the substrate COD was estimated at $1.20 \text{ g COD-g VS}^{-1}$ [28]. The detailed characteristics of this substrate are available in previous studies [28]. To fulfil the European legislation (Official Journal of the European Union, L 54, 26 February 2011), the mixture underwent a hygienisation step at 70°C for 1h, after dilution to 20% of VS with distilled water.

Two different inocula were used in the first fermentation step. Activated sludge (AS) was collected after the secondary clarifier tank from an urban wastewater treatment plant. It was concentrated by centrifugation to $112.8 \text{ g TS-L}^{-1}$ and used directly as inoculum without storage or pretreatment. In fermentation reactor, the AS concentration was adjusted to 25 g TS-L^{-1} . Compost leachate (CL) was collected from a green-waste composting plant and similarly used as inoculum. The collected CL contained 5.5 g TS-L^{-1} , corresponding to a concentration of 2.4 g TS-L^{-1} in the reactor. Between collection and the start of the fermentation (maximum of 1 or 2 days), the inocula were stored in

closed containers at 4°C to avoid as much as possible their evolution.

The raw effluent from the first fermentation stage was used as both substrate and inoculum for the second stage, without any treatment other than adjusting its pH to 7. No external inoculum was added in the second stage.

2.2. Experimental set-up

The first-stage lactic fermentation was carried out in a 3L batch reactor (Applikon Bio 3L, Gethinge, Göteborg, Sweden), with a 2L working volume. The pH was continuously maintained at 4.5 with the automatic addition of 3M NaOH, and the temperature was kept at 35°C using a heating blanket; both parameters were recorded every 3 min. The pressure was measured every 20 s with a manometer (LEO3, Keller, Winterthur, Switzerland) and released through a peristaltic pump (Masterflex L/S 7554-85, Cole Parmer, Vernon Hills, IL, USA) as soon as it reached 1070 mbar. FW concentration was adjusted to 100 g VS-L^{-1} by dilution with distilled water with a substrate-to-activated sludge ratio of 4 on a VS basis, and substrate-to-compost leachate ratio of 42 on a VS basis. The batch fermentation was carried out until the lactate concentration reached a plateau (~ 11 days), with liquid samples collected daily for metabolite quantification. The operating conditions were defined based on the work of Chenebault et al. [29], who achieved a concentration of about 70 g L^{-1} of lactic acid under similar batch conditions with 200 g VS-L^{-1} of food waste.

The second-stage fermentation was carried out in 600 mL flasks (working volume of 200 mL), incubated at 30°C for 10 to 14 days, until gas production ceased. Total gas production was estimated from daily pressure measurements, and liquid samples were collected daily for metabolite analysis and pH measurement.

The operating conditions for the first and second fermentation stages are summarised in Table 1. The first fermentation stage employed either AS or CL as inoculum to obtain distinct microbial communities and metabolite profiles. One reactor was set for each inoculum. The second fermentation stage was performed in batch mode, without any other inoculation, in order to evaluate the impact of the different microbial communities and metabolite profiles from the first step on the lactate conversion. The effluents from each reactor were collected and distributed into four individual flasks per condition. Consequently, four replicates for the “AS-derived effluent” condition and four replicates for the “CL-derived effluent” condition were set up for the second-stage fermentation. Samples for metabolite analysis were taken daily, and samples for microbial composition were collected at the beginning and the end of the second fermentation in the individual flasks.

2.3. Analytical methods

Metabolite concentrations in the liquid phase were measured using two analytical methods. VFA were quantified by gas chromatography (Clarus 580 from PerkinElmer) equipped with an autosampler. Separation was achieved on an Alltech FFAP EC 1000 (15m) coupled with a flame ionisation detector (FID) at 280°C . Nitrogen was used as a gas carrier at a flow rate of 6 mL min^{-1} . VFAs were quantified in a range between 0.1 and 1.0 g L^{-1} ($\pm 2\%$). Before analysis, samples were filtered through a $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ nylon filter and diluted in half using an internal standard. To complement the GC analysis, HPLC (High-Performance Liquid Chromatography) was also used to quantify VFAs, other carboxylic acids and alcohols (glycerol, ethanol, 1,3-propanediol, formic acid, fumaric acid, succinic acid, lactic acid, pyruvic acid), in concentrations varying between 0.1 and 10 g L^{-1} . Separation was performed on an Aminex HPX-87H $300 \times 7.8 \text{ mm}$ (Bio Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) column, after passing through a protective pre-column (MicroGuard cation H refill cartridges, Bio Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). The detection was done with a refractometer. Samples were filtered through a $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ filter and adjusted to a pH between 1 and 4 using a sulfuric acid solution before analysis.

Table 1

Operating conditions of the two-stage fermentation. [FW] stands for food waste concentration, S/X stands for substrate-to-inoculum ratio (g VS·g VS⁻¹), [Lac] stands for lactate concentration.

First stage			Second stage			Condition Name
Inoculum	Operating Conditions	Batch Time	Substrate and Inoculum	Operating conditions	Batch time	
AS	pH 4.5 T = 35°C [FW] = 100 g VS·L ⁻¹ S/X = 4 g VS·g VS ⁻¹ Working volume = 2000 mL Reactor volume = 3000 mL	11 days	Total Effluent	pH initial 7 T = 30°C [Lac] = 22.21 ± 2.46 g L ⁻¹ Working volume = 100 mL Reactor volume = 600 mL	10 days	AS_Total
CL	pH 4.5 T = 35°C [FW] = 100 g VS·L ⁻¹ S/X = 42 g VS·g VS ⁻¹ Working volume = 2000 mL Reactor volume = 3000 mL	11 days	Total Effluent	pH initial 7 T = 30°C [Lac] = 38.92 ± 2.74 g L ⁻¹ Working volume = 100 mL Reactor volume = 600 mL	14 days	CL_Total

2.4. Calculations and statistical analysis

Metabolite concentrations were expressed as grams of chemical oxygen demand per litre (g COD·L⁻¹), calculated from the theoretical COD of each individual molecule. The FW introduced in the first fermentation represented the initial biodegradable COD, adjusted to 128 g COD·L⁻¹. Samples taken from the four flasks at the beginning and the end of the second-stage fermentation were used for the COD balance, notably for calculating the yield of individual metabolites relative to the initial FW (Equation (1)), and the final selectivity of propionate relative to total metabolite production (Equation (2)).

$$\text{Yield of individual metabolite} = \frac{\text{Final COD concentration of the metabolite}}{\text{Introduced biodegradable COD concentration of FW}} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$\text{Selectivity of individual metabolite} = \frac{\text{Final COD concentration of the metabolite}}{\text{Total metabolites COD concentration}} \times 100 \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

The mean and the standard deviation of the four biological replicates of the second fermentation for each condition were calculated and used for comparison. The final propionate yield from the introduced food waste and the final propionate selectivity were statistically compared between the two conditions: CL-derived effluent or AS-derived effluent, each of them containing four replicates. To verify the suitability of the data for ANOVA test, the normality of the residuals was assessed using the Shapiro test, and the homoscedasticity was assessed using the Levene test. ANOVA test was then applied to determine whether the initial inoculum (CL or AS) had a significant effect on propionate yield and propionate selectivity. This approach makes it possible to assess the biological conversion of the introduced COD into various metabolites of interest, with particular attention paid to propionate production.

In addition, the propionate produced in the second stage, calculated as the difference between the final and initial propionate concentrations (in g·L⁻¹) in the flasks, was compared with the lactate consumed during the second stage, calculated as the difference between the initial and final lactate concentrations (in g·L⁻¹). This ratio represents the specific yield of propionate from the lactate consumed and was compared to the theoretical value reported for pure propionate fermentations.

2.5. Microbial analysis

Samples were collected at the initial and final time points of the first stage using AS or CL as inoculum, and at the initial and final time points of the second stage. Samples of 1.5 mL were centrifuged at 13,500 rpm for 15 min. The resulting pellets were used for DNA extraction, purification, and sequencing of the V3-V4 region of 16S rDNA [30]. The sequences were submitted to the European Nucleotide Archive under the Bioproject n° PRJEB68972. Total bacteria quantification was done using qPCR as described by Perat et al. [31]. The total number of 16S copies per sample was multiplied by the relative abundance of each genus to estimate the total abundance of each genus. Then, the difference in total

abundance of each genus between the final and initial time points of the fermentation was calculated to estimate bacterial growth [32]. The total abundances are expressed as the number of copies of the 16S gene, without calculating log₁₀ or ratio, because of the presence of zero values. Microbial community data were analysed using R packages *phyloseq* and *microeco* to calculate and visualise relative and total abundances at the genus level.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Influence of different mixed cultures on metabolite production

The first fermentation stage aimed to produce lactate from FW using two distinct microbial communities, inoculated either with activated sludge (AS) or compost leachate (CL). The objective of the second step of fermentation was the conversion of lactate into propionate and acetate by the indigenous microorganisms present in the effluent. The results of the second-stage fermentation were evaluated based on the type of effluent used, coming from the first-stage fermentation inoculated with AS or CL (Fig. 1).

The two inocula used for the first-stage fermentation led to distinct metabolite profiles (Fig. 1). When using AS as an inoculum, heterolactic fermentation occurred during the first stage, producing lactate, acetate, and ethanol simultaneously. Traces of other VFAs (i.e., butyrate and propionate) and succinate were also detected. Lactate reached 22.21 ± 2.46 g L⁻¹ in the effluent to be used in the second stage, representing 53.89 ± 2.96% of total metabolites (measured in COD). In contrast, homolactic fermentation dominated with CL inoculum,

Fig. 1. Initial and final concentrations of metabolites during the second-stage fermentation, using effluent from the first-stage fermentation inoculated with activated sludge (AS) or compost leachate (CL). “Others” include isobutyrate, isovalerate, valerate, isocaproate and caproate, detected in concentrations below 1 g L⁻¹.

resulting in lactate as the main product ($38.92 \pm 2.74 \text{ g L}^{-1}$), representing 94.52% of the total metabolites COD with only minor traces of ethanol and acetate. Despite these differences, the overall conversion yield of FW was similar with both inocula, ranging from 35.15 to $39.90 \pm 4.55\%$ g COD of total metabolites per g COD of FW when using CL or AS as inoculum, respectively. The predominance of heterolactic or homolactic fermentation can likely be attributed to differences in lactic acid bacteria (LAB) communities present in the inocula. LAB represent a wide range of Gram + bacteria belonging to the *Lactobacillales* order, capable of fermenting carbohydrates to lactate through different pathways depending on the genes present in their genome, which encode different enzymes leading to homo or heterolactic fermentation. Homofermentative LAB produce 2 mol of lactate per mole of hexose, while heterofermentative LAB produce lactate and either ethanol (1 mol ethanol + 1 mol lactate per mole of hexose) or acetate (1 mol acetate + 1 mol lactate per mole of pentose) [33]. For instance, the genera *Lactobacillus* and *Lactococcus* are generally homofermentative, while *Leuconostoc*, *Weissella*, and *Oenococcus* predominantly perform heterolactic fermentation [34]. Stoichiometric calculations suggest that with AS inoculum, several fermentation pathways likely occurred in parallel: heterolactic fermentation to acetate and lactate (0.13 M of each metabolite) and to ethanol and lactate (0.10 M of each metabolite). The remaining lactate (0.06 M) could have been produced by homolactic fermentation. Some LAB can also produce succinate through citrate metabolism [33]. By contrast, the CL inoculum led to nearly exclusive lactate production, indicating homolactic fermentation, therefore suggesting a microbial community composition likely dominated by homofermentative LAB.

During the second-stage fermentation, all lactate was consumed, leading to different concentrations of propionate, acetate, and butyrate depending on the initial effluent composition. For the AS-inoculated effluent, lactate was fully consumed within two days (Fig. 2), whereas in CL-inoculated effluent, lactate depletion was nearly complete only after ten days. The different VFAs were produced simultaneously, and concomitantly with lactate consumption, suggesting that lactate was converted into propionate, acetate and butyrate. The pH remained between 6.5 and 7 for both conditions, without any substantial drop.

Fig. 2. Dynamic evolution of the metabolites concentration and pH during the second stage, using A) Activated sludge-derived effluent and B) Compost Leachate-derived effluent.

Interestingly, for both conditions, the cumulative COD of metabolites at the end of the second stage was higher than the initial COD, suggesting that some unquantified compounds in the first step (likely carbohydrate residues) were converted into metabolites (butyrate, isobutyrate, isovalerate, caproate, and some propionate) during the second stage (Fig. 1).

Regarding the propionate production, with AS-inoculated first-stage effluent, propionate reached $14.30 \pm 0.52 \text{ g L}^{-1}$, representing $37.33 \pm 1.41\%$ of total COD of metabolites. Using CL-inoculated first-stage effluent, propionate reached even higher concentrations (up to $17.90 \pm 0.35 \text{ g L}^{-1}$), resulting from the higher initial lactate concentration and selectivity. It was the main metabolite, representing $45.51 \pm 1.81\%$ of total COD metabolites, followed by acetate ($11.89 \pm 0.52 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) and butyrate ($7.20 \pm 1.16 \text{ g L}^{-1}$). These results indicate that the two-stage lactate-propionate process is highly selective for propionate production, even when using mixed cultures. Furthermore, the propionate concentrations obtained are substantially higher than those reported by Wu et al. [26], who obtained a maximum of 3 g L^{-1} (around 4.8 and 5.9 times higher for the AS-inoculated and CL-inoculated effluents, respectively), using a similar two-stage process. These findings are highly promising for selectively produce high-concentration of propionate from FW, as such concentrations and selectivity have never been reported previously. However, these concentrations are still far below those obtained with simple substrates and pure cultures of *Propionibacterium* and *Acidipropionibacterium*, the model microorganisms for propionic fermentation. For instance, in fed-batch fermentation of glycerol by *P. acidipropionici* in a fibrous-bed bioreactor, propionate concentration reached 106 g L^{-1} and up to 43.40 g L^{-1} in batch mode [35]. These bacteria are able to use glycerol, lactate, or sugars as carbon sources for propionate production through the Wood-Werkman cycle [35,36]. The theoretical yield of propionate produced from lactate is 0.55 g g^{-1} , a value nearly reached in pure

cultures [37]. In the present study, this yield was $0.61 \pm 0.03 \text{ g g}^{-1}$ with AS-inoculated effluent and $0.49 \pm 0.04 \text{ g g}^{-1}$ with CL-inoculated effluent, indicating that mixed cultures can be at least as efficient as pure propionic acid bacteria in converting lactate to propionate. In the AS-inoculated effluent condition, propionate production exceeded the theoretical yield expected from lactate conversion alone. This additional propionate likely originated from other metabolic pathways, such as the conversion of residual carbohydrates or protein-derived compounds released during food-waste degradation. The quantification of the gaseous production, i.e. H_2 and CO_2 gases, could have contributed to a more complete characterisation of the metabolic pathways, but these parameters were not measured in the present study. In particular, CO_2 may be produced from carbon sources during either FW or lactate degradation, and may be consumed during propionate production via the Wood-Ljungdahl or Wood-Werkman pathways [36,38]. Meanwhile, H_2 production may be associated with the production of butyrate [39]. While CL-inoculated fermentation yielded higher propionate concentration, the conversion yield of lactate to propionate was slightly lower. In addition, the efficiency of lactate conversion to propionate seems to depend on the initial lactate concentration and selectivity, as it was different for both inocula, reaching a higher value with the AS inoculum, while initial lactate production was lower.

The influence of the inoculum used in the first stage (CL vs AS) on propionate selectivity in the final effluent, including all metabolites, and on the overall propionate yield from FW was evaluated (Fig. 3). Using CL resulted in significantly higher propionate yield and selectivity at the end of the two-stage fermentation, although lactate-to-propionate conversion yield was slightly lower in this case. However, the butyrate production was substantially higher than with AS, representing nearly 20% of the total metabolites, suggesting that part of the lactate was converted to butyrate [26]. Consequently, the specific yield of lactate to propionate was reduced, despite the higher final propionate concentration achieved with this inoculum. As both butyrate and propionate producers are able to use lactate, the co-existence of these two metabolic pathways when lactate is available in high concentrations is expected. In contrast, under lower lactate concentrations, as observed in the AS-inoculated fermentation, the most favourable lactate-conversion

pathway may have dominated, namely the production of propionate and acetate, which is thermodynamically and energetically more favourable than the production of butyrate [26]. These results suggest that the propionate selectivity is influenced by the initial composition of the first-stage effluent, in particular by lactate selectivity. The presence of additional metabolites in the first-stage effluent may further influence the metabolic pathways expressed during the second stage. These differences might also be due to different microbial communities, as will be discussed later.

Therefore, these results suggest that the first fermentation step is the limiting step for propionate production in two-stage fermentation systems, as higher lactate concentrations and selectivity achieved in the first step led to higher propionate production in the second stage. Nonetheless, it remains unclear whether the observed difference in propionate yield and selectivity in the second stage was driven by the composition of the microbial communities associated with the different inocula (AS or CL) or by the lactate concentration and selectivity. Detailed analysis of the microbial communities could provide insights into the mechanisms governing propionate production in the second stage.

3.2. Microbial community analysis

The compositions of microbial communities in the first stage using AS and CL inocula are shown in Fig. 4, while those of the second stage are presented in Fig. 5 for different types of effluent (from AS-inoculated or CL-inoculated fermentations).

In the first stage, the initial microbial community of the AS inoculum was highly diverse, whereas the CL inoculum was dominated by *Streptococcus* sp. (a lactic acid bacterium), *Thiopseudomonas* sp., and *Arco-bacter* sp. The observed alpha diversity at the start of AS inoculated fermentation ranged from 1335 to 1380 OTU, compared with only 534 OTU for CL inoculated fermentation. By the end of the first fermentation step, *Lactobacillus* sp. became the dominant genus under all conditions, reaching 99.85 and $91.89 \pm 4.52\%$ in the CL-inoculated and the AS-inoculated fermentations (Fig. 4). The final observed alpha diversity was 278-298 OTU for AS and 38 OTU for CL. The presence of these

Fig. 3. Statistical analysis of process performance depending on the inoculum used during the first fermentation stage. An ANOVA test was performed on the dataset to compare the two experimental groups, namely AS-derived effluent and CL-derived effluent, each containing four replicates each. The p-value for the propionate selectivity was 0.00038 and 0.000025 for the propionate yield. Both p-values suggested significant differences between the groups, clustered in different statistical groups (a and b).

Fig. 4. Relative abundance of the 15 most abundant genera at the beginning (D0) and at the end (Df) of the first-stage fermentation. The first 2 bars correspond to the activated sludge inoculum condition (AS), while the last two to the compost leachate inoculum condition (CL).

Fig. 5. Relative abundance of the 15 most abundant genera during the second-stage fermentation for initial (T0) and final days (Tf), using A) AS inoculum and B) CL inoculum in the first stage.

additional OTUs in AS-fermented effluent may contribute to the broader metabolite profile observed under this condition, specifically the higher acetate production, which is a main product of *Acetobacter* metabolism, which was detected in a 5.90% of relative abundance at the end of the fermentation inoculated with AS [40]. The initial community structure, in terms of both composition and diversity, likely contributed to fermentation pathways and the development of the bacteria over time. In addition, the initial concentration of the inoculum and its ratio with the substrate likely drove the microbial dynamics: the higher microbial concentration in the AS condition favoured the growth of a broader range of bacteria. In contrast, the higher substrate pressure in the initial CL condition may have selected for more resistant and faster-growing bacteria, such as members of the *Lactobacillus* genus. This difference is intrinsically related to the inoculum characteristics as collected from the environment. Nonetheless, the *Lactobacillus* genus remained the main actor of lactate fermentation from FW in both inocula, consistent with previous studies [29,41,42].

In the second-stage fermentation with AS-inoculated effluent, the initial community mainly contained *Lactobacillus* sp. ($87.13 \pm 1.62\%$). By the end of this second stage fermentation, the community had diversified, comprising *Lactobacillus* sp. ($26.81 \pm 0.34\%$), *Anaerospobacter* sp. ($21.03 \pm 12.50\%$), *Sporanaerobacter* sp. ($21.29 \pm 2.88\%$), *Caproiciproducens* sp. ($7.74 \pm 7.38\%$), and, to a lesser extent, *Tyzzerella* sp. ($3.58 \pm 2.22\%$), and some clusters of *Clostridium* (Fig. 5). Quantification of the number of gene copies indicated possible growth of *Sporanaerobacter* sp., *Anaerospobacter* sp., *Caproiciproducens* sp., *Tyzzerella* sp., *Clostridium_sensu_stricto* 7, 11, 15 and 2 sp. with an increased number of 16S gene copies during the second fermentation. Meanwhile, the populations of *Lactobacillus* sp., *Aeriscardovia* sp., and *Clostridium_sensu_stricto* 1 sp. decreased (Fig. 6).

With CL-inoculated effluent, the initial microbial community of the second stage was dominated by *Lactobacillus* sp. ($98.65 \pm 1.44\%$), selected during the first-stage lactic fermentation. At the end of the second stage, *Lactobacillus* sp. decreased to $6.38 \pm 1.56\%$, with *Anaerospobacter* sp. ($36.87 \pm 9.19\%$), *Clostridium_sensu_stricto* 11 ($18.99 \pm 8.07\%$), *Clostridium_sensu_stricto* 18 ($8.16 \pm 2.03\%$), *Clostridium_sensu_stricto* 15 ($7.48 \pm 3.05\%$), and *unclassified Clostridiaceae* 1 ($6.22 \pm 4.54\%$) being the main genera. In particular, genera including

Fig. 6. Bacterial growth during the second-stage fermentation, based on the absolute abundance differences between final and initial times (copies of 16S/mL), using A) AS effluent and B) CL effluent.

Anaerospobacter sp., *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_11*, *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_18*, *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_15*, *unclassified Clostridiaceae_1*, *Tyzzerella* sp. and *unclassified Family_XI* exhibited increased 16S gene copy numbers, reflecting their growth during the second stage (Fig. 6). On the contrary, the *Lactobacillus* genus demonstrated a decrease during the second stage.

The increase in the abundance of these genera may reflect their involvement in the conversion of lactate to propionate and acetate. *Anaerospobacter* sp., which rose in both propionate fermentations, has previously been reported to produce propionate in gut microbiota [43]. Members of this genus may have played a similar role in the current fermentation, potentially contributing to the production of propionate from lactate. Similarly, Xu et al. [44] observed an increase in the *Tyzzerella* genus in the microbial community during batch fermentation of FW into lactate over several cycles, associated with the conversion of lactate into propionate and acetate, which aligns with the present observations with both inocula. Members of this genus could likely participate in the conversion of lactate into propionate and acetate in the present study. Moreover, the genus *Clostridium* includes a broad range of species with diverse fermentative capabilities, some of which can produce propionate through the acrylate pathway, especially *Clostridium propionicum* and *Clostridium neopropionicum*, recently reclassified as *Anaerotignum propionicum* and *Anaerotignum neopropionicum* [45].

For example, *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_7*, identified as *Clostridium novyi*, converts D-lactate to propionate and acetate through the acrylate pathway [46]. This cluster of *Clostridium* was found in the present study and rose in the second stage, which may be related to this metabolic activity. Other clusters of *Clostridium* observed in the fermentation may

include species possessing the enzymes for the acrylate pathway. For example, Cibis et al. [47] observed the production of propionate, acetate, and butyrate in some isolates belonging to *Clostridium cochlearium* and *Clostridium tetani*. In the present samples, the sequences identified as *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_15* (from OTU grouped at 99% identity) aligned with 100% coverage with these species (Blastn with core nt database), suggesting that *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_15* might be *Clostridium cochlearium* and/or *Clostridium tetani*, therefore contributing to propionate and acetate production. The recurrent enrichment of these bacterial genera (*Anaerospobacter*, *Tyzzerella*, *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_15*, *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_11*), regardless of the inoculum origin (AS or CL), suggests that the process operation shapes the microbial communities towards the specific production of propionate and acetate from lactate, supporting the identification of these microorganisms as potential propionate producers. In addition, the possible growth of *Sporanaerobacter* and *Caproiciproducens* may be related to the production of caproate, detected at $0.07 \pm 0.014 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ in the final effluent. More specifically, *Sporanaerobacter* sp. can produce acetate or butyrate from lactate as intermediates for chain elongation in the presence of high ethanol concentrations [48,49]. *Caproiciproducens* has already been identified to produce caproate using lactate as substrate in previous studies [50]. However, the metabarcoding methodology used in this study, based on the amplification of a region of the 16S rRNA gene, provides taxonomic information on bacterial or archaeal communities, generally at the genus level depending on the amplified region and database resolution. Functional interpretations can therefore be cautiously inferred from the detected taxa and from metabolic traits previously described in the literature for related genera or species. When such tools as the BLASTn tool (NCBI) are used, OTUs or ASVs may, in some cases, be associated with a closely related species. However, these assignments should be interpreted with caution, as 16S RNA gene sequences often do not provide sufficient resolution for reliable species-level identification. Therefore, a deeper investigation, including metagenomics and meta-transcriptomics, would be required to associate microorganisms with a specific metabolic activity. Furthermore, rare species, although not dominant, may also contribute to the metabolic conversion observed [51]. In addition, their quantification using the qPCR of 16S rDNA and relative abundance might be underestimated compared to the real amount of cells present, as demonstrated by Tettamanti Boshier et al. [32] for species with a relative abundance of less than 10%. This method of quantification therefore suffers from bias from both qPCR and 16S sequencing methods. It only allows for estimating the main genera present in the samples, but does not provide an exhaustive quantification of specific species. Moreover, the conditions required for efficient propionate production from lactate remain only partially understood, because it is challenging to differentiate the respective effects of the carbon substrate (lactate) and concentration, the initial microbial community structure, and the operating conditions. Indeed, it has been demonstrated earlier that the initial lactate level influences both the final propionate concentration and the specific lactate-to-propionate conversion yield. The slightly lower yield observed with the CL-inoculated fermentation may also be related to the development of different microbial communities, in particular with the increased abundance of a broad range of *Clostridium*-related bacteria. Even though some members are capable of producing propionate from lactate, others have also been identified to produce butyrate from lactate conversion [39,52]. This suggests that lactate production in the first stage both drives microbial selection in the second stage and influences metabolic pathways, finally impacting the final production profile.

Despite these uncertainties, the current study highlights the potential for high-concentration selective propionate production from FW using mixed culture, achieving up to $17.90 \pm 0.35 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ of propionate. To the authors' knowledge, such propionate concentrations have not been reported before for mixed cultures treating food waste under two-stage fermentation. This is consistent with previous studies of Wu et al. (2023) and Yin et al. (2025) [26,53], who implemented similar

strategies for the selective conversion of lactate to propionate using mixed cultures, although they reached only 3 and 8 g L⁻¹ of propionate, respectively. The increase in final product concentration addresses a major challenge in the application of acidogenic fermentation of organic waste for the production and downstream utilisation of bio-based VFAs [54]. For an economically feasible downstream process, propionate concentration should be close to 100 g L⁻¹, as reported by Gonzalez-Garcia et al. (2017). Such concentrations have so far only been achieved in pure cultures [55]. The lactate-based route thus appears to be a highly promising strategy for selective propionate production, highlighting the potential of eco-engineering strategies using mixed communities to target specific propionate pathways. This approach avoids the need for pure cultivation techniques, as previously required for direct production of a specific metabolite, or in bioaugmentation-based strategies used as a lever for selectivity [56]. This strategy offers a simpler process for waste valorisation towards a specific VFA using environmental inocula, avoiding the costs associated with medium preparation and sterilisation required for the pure culture systems. In contrast with previous studies on directed acidogenic fermentation of organic wastes [11], the present results emphasise the role of controlling the metabolic pathways through lactate to achieve a high propionate selectivity, beyond the sole effect of pH and temperature. Future research should focus on optimising FW conversion into lactate to maximise the conversion yield above 50%, together with a deeper understanding of the metabolic pathways and microorganisms driving these conversions, as the functioning of mixed microbial ecosystems still contains many unsolved mechanisms.

4. Conclusion

The two-stage fermentation strategy via the lactate route efficiently improved both the concentration and selectivity of propionate from FW, achieving concentrations of up to 17.90 ± 0.35 g L⁻¹ when compost leachate was used as inoculum during the first stage. The high concentration and selectivity of lactate in the first stage acted as sufficient drivers for the selection of the propionate production pathways. The recurrent presence of *Anaerospobacter* sp., *Tyzzerella* sp., and *Clostridium* sp., during the second fermentation indicates that mixed microbial communities can be steered towards targeted propionate production without the need for pure cultures. These findings build on previous work and pave the way for a more in-depth exploration of microbial interactions and the underlying metabolic pathways, with the potential to further optimise selectivity and yield in future applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mathilde Bourgeois: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Lucia Braga-Nan:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Gaëlle Santa-Catalina:** Data curation, Investigation. **Renaud Escudié:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Nicolas Bernet:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Eric Trably:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Eric Trably reports financial support was provided by European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the financial support of the BIOCTANE project with Grant N° 101084336. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them. The authors would like to acknowledge INRAE Bio2E Facility (Bio2E, INRAE, 2018. Environmental Biotechnology and Biorefinery Facility (<https://doi.org/10.15454/1.557234103446854E12>), where part of the experiments were conducted.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2026.109757>.

Data availability

Data are available on the depository Zenodo under the designation 10.5281/zenodo.17779775.

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